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Production of biopolymeric energy nanocomposite

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Introduction: The present study aims to develop an energetic material (ME) based on a biopolymeric nanocomposite. Based on an energetic material widely used in Termite welding, composed of iron/aluminum oxide (Fe₂O₃/Al) (1). The insertion of polymers in the formulation gives the ME physical and chemical properties, influences some properties, for example, the amount of gas released during burning and the sensitivity to ignition (2) Another advantage of its use, for example, is the reduction of corrosion, a phenomenon easily suffered in ME that contains Al powder in the formulation. This corrosion invalidates the energetic compound and still carries security risks. In order to increase the stability of the ME making its handling, transport, storage and application safer, xanthan gum and polyaniline were used to improve the ignition of the material by electrical stimulus.

Methods: The polymeric matrix is composed of a mixture between xanthan gum and polyaniline (PAni), the production of ME is carried out in two stages. The first comprises the synthesis of PAni nanoparticles following the in situ polymerization route. In situ polymerization is based on the dispersion of xanthan gum in the solution containing monomer so that polymer formation can occur between the gum particles, thus obtaining a more intimate mixture between the phases. The first step is the synthesis of PAni. Xanthan gum insertion was carried out in two different ways. The first “a” in which 0.5 g of xanthan is dissolved in 100 ml of 1molar aqueous solution of sulfuric acid, and after homogenization 0.5 ml of aniline is added by dripping to the reaction medium, after dissolution it is added 10 mL of 1 molar aqueous solution of sulfuric acid, with 2.5 g of ammonium persulfate. The reaction medium was under ambient atmosphere, kept under constant agitation with the aid of a mechanical stirrer at 700 rpm and at room temperature. The time required to perform this step was 2 hours. The second “b” follows the same reaction parameters, however the xanthan gum is inserted into the reaction medium dissolved in 10 mL of 1 molar aqueous solution of sulfuric acid, with 2.5 g of ammonium persulfate. The time required to produce matrix “b” was 2 h and 20 min. The second stage consists of the homogenization of 0.2 grams of the polymeric matrix, with the termite in the proportion 1/1 v / v of Fe₂O₃ / Al. The formulations were produced in triplicate, submitted to shear homogenization for 5 min, later conditioned in a cylindrical mold, with the aid of a porcelain piston, it was pressed applying manual force, during 10 s to guarantee the compaction of the energetic material. The specimens have a total mass of 1 g. They were characterized by fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and burning tests were performed.

Results & Discussions: The results showed that there was no chemical modification of the inputs, the peaks shown in the FTIR result are characteristic of each material present in the formulation, and the firing tests indicate that the termite remains effective for welding applications, since the test demonstrated the capacity to completely melt 1 gram of metal alloy.

Conclusions: The material obtained in this preliminary phase of the study is promising. In the future, we intend to characterize this energetic material through thermal and chemical analyzes seeking the evaluation of combustion heat, chemical stability, heat of explosion, identification of compounds generated by the thermal decomposition of the biopolymeric energy nanocomposite.

Key words: *Energy materials, Nanocomposites, Biopolymers*

References

1. Conkling, J. A., Chistry of Pyrotechnics: Basic Principles and Theory, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1985.
2. CHRIS MOCELLA , JOHN A. CONKLING ,Chemistry of Pyrotechnics: Basic Principles and Theory, ed.3^o, 2019.

